

ASTRONOMIYADAN BA'ZI MASALALAR VA ULARNING YECHIM USULLARI PYTHON DASTURIDA KODLAR ORQALI TUSHUNTIRISH

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import math
Q = 0
q = 0
a = 0
T = 0
V = 0
aq = 0
aQ = 0
soz = ""
jav = ""
sozi = ""

print("*****
*****")
print("*   Astronomiyadan masalalar yechadigan dasturga xush kelibsiz!   *")
print("*****
*****\n")

while True:
print("Qaysi parametrni topmoqchisiz.....")
print("1.a-Sayyora orbitasining katta yarim o'qi")
print("2.V-Sayyoraning o'rtacha orbital tezligi")
print("3.Perigeliy va afeliy masofalari")

soz = input()
if soz == "a" or soz == "1":

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print("Sizga aynan qaysi parametr kerak.....")
print("1.a-Sayyora orbitasining katta yarim o'qi")
print("2.Q-Sayyoraning afeliy masofasi")
print("3.q-Sayyoraning perigeliy masofasi")
sozi = input()
if sozi == "a" or sozi == "1":
    print("afeliy masofasini kiriting.....")
    Q = float(input())
    print("perigeliy masofasini kiriting.....")
    q = float(input())
    print("Sayyora orbitasining katta yarim o'qi= ", (q + Q) / 2)
    for i in range(10):
        print("*", end="")
elif sozi == "Q" or sozi == "2":
    print("Sayyora orbitasining katta yarim o'qini kiriting.....")
    a = float(input())
    print("perigeliy masofasini kiriting.....")
    q = float(input())
    print("Sayyoraning afeliy masofasi= ", 2 * a - q)
    for i in range(10):
        print("*", end="")
elif sozi == "q" or sozi == "3":
    print("Sayyora orbitasining katta yarim o'qini kiriting.....")
    a = float(input())
    print("Sayyoraning afeliy masofasini kiriting.....")
    Q = float(input())
    print("Sayyoraning perigeliy masofasi= ", 2 * a - Q)
    for i in range(10):
        print("*", end="")
```

Rasm-2:


```
C:\WINDOWS\py.exe
Qaysi parametrni topmoqchisiz....
1.a-Sayyora orbitasining katta yarim o'qi
2.V-Sayyoraning o'rtacha orbital tezligi
3.Perigeliy va afeliy masofalari
2
Sizga aynan qaysi parametr kerak....
1.V-Sayyoraning orbital tezligi
2.a-Sayyoraning orbita radiusi
3.T-Sayyoraning quyosh atrofida aylanish davri
1
Sayyoraning orbita radiusini kiriting....
270
Sayyoraning quyosh atrofida aylanish davrini kiriting....
365
Sayyoraning orbital tezligi= 4.64783570668079
*
*
*
*
*
*
*
Qaysi parametrni topmoqchisiz....
1.a-Sayyora orbitasining katta yarim o'qi
2.V-Sayyoraning o'rtacha orbital tezligi
3.Perigeliy va afeliy masofalari
```

```
elif sozi == "a" or sozi == "2":
    print("Sayyoraning orbital tezligini kiriting.....")
    V = float(input())
    print("Sayyoraning quyosh atrofida aylanish davrini kiriting.....")
    T = float(input())
    print("Sayyoraning orbita radiusi a= ", (V * T) / (2 * math.pi))
    for i in range(10):
        print("*", end="")
    elif sozi == "T" or sozi == "3":
        print("Sayyoraning orbital tezligini kiriting.....")
        V = float(input())
        print("Sayyoraning orbita radiusini kiriting.....")
        a = float(input())
        print("Sayyoraning quyosh atrofida aylanish davrini kiriting T= ", (2 * math.pi *
a) / V)
    for i in range(10):
        print("*", end="")
    elif soz == "Perigeliy va afeliy masofalari" or soz == "3":
        print("Sizga aynan qaysi parametr kerak.....")
        print("1.q-Sayyoraning perigeliy masofasi")
```


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```
print("2.Q-Sayyoraning afeliy masofasi")
print("3.aq-Sayyora orbitasining katta yarim o'qini perigeliy masofasi orqali
topish")
print("4.aQ-Sayyora orbitasining katta yarim o'qini afeliy masofasi orqali
topish")
sozi = input()
if sozi == "q" or sozi == "1":
print("Sayyoraning orbita radiusini kiriting.....")
a = float(input())
print("Sayyoraning quyosh atrofida aylanish eksentrisitetini kiriting.....")
e = float(input())
print("Sayyoraning perigeliy masofasi q= ", a * (1 - e))
for i in range(10):
print("*", end="")
elif sozi == "Q" or sozi == "2":
print("Sayyoraning orbita radiusini kiriting.....")
a = float(input())
print("Sayyoraning quyosh atrofida aylanish eksentrisitetini kiriting.....")
e = float(input())
print("Sayyoraning afeliy masofasi Q= ", a * (1 + e))
for i in range(10):
print("*", end="")
```

